

Surgical manegment of deep neck space infections

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Abstract:

With the advancing era of antibiotics, incidence of deep neck space infections largely decreased due to early identification and treatment of pharyngeal, tonsillar and odontogenic infections. Deep neck space infections need to be identified and treated early to prevent extension into danger space which may result in severe life threatening complications or even death. Cases of deep neck space infections, are going to be presented with course of treatment and different lines of management for each patient.

Axial Neck CT scan for a patient with showing parapharyngeal abscess.

Evaluation Of The Bucket Test In Vestibular Disorders

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Abstract:

Objective: To evaluate the use of the bucket test as a screening test in the evaluation of vestibular disorders.

Methods: Inclusion criteria: subjects older than 18 years with some vestibular disorder. The visual subjective vertical was assessed binocularly using the bucket test. Five measurements were made in a clockwise direction and five in the counterclockwise direction.

Results: Fifty healthy volunteers were included and mean normal values ranged from -1.0° to $+3.0^{\circ}$. In addition, there were 80 volunteers with vestibular disorders. 55 were women with an average age of 53 years. The total average value found was $0.91^{\circ} \pm 2.8^{\circ}$ SD for all subjects and $2.60^{\circ} \pm 1.88^{\circ}$ SD without negative numbers (affected side) Results in benign paroxysmal postural vertigo (51 subjects) were: $0.71^{\circ} \pm 3.10^{\circ}$ SD before the epley maneuver and: $0.57^{\circ} \pm 2.16^{\circ}$ SD after the epley maneuver. The deviation corresponded to the altered side in: 57% of the subjects BPPB. In the case of patients with Ménière's disease (25 subjects) the results were: $1.22^{\circ} \pm 2.61^{\circ}$ SD and without negative numbers: $2.74^{\circ} \pm 2.03^{\circ}$ SD. The deviation corresponded to the altered side in: 52% of Ménière's disease. The results in patients with vestibular migraine (2 subjects) were: $0.2 \pm 0.14^{\circ}$ SD.

Conclusion: We observed that in patients the side of the deviation corresponded to 56% of the altered vestibular side. The average ($0.91^{\circ} \pm 2.8^{\circ}$ SD) fell in the normal range (-1.0° to $+3.0^{\circ}$) but, however, in pathologies with active crisis, the values tended to be modified towards the affected vestibular side.

Key words:

Bucket test, subjective visual vertical, otoliths.

Endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy with marsupialization of the lacrimal sac

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Abstract:

Objective: To analyze the efficacy of endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy (DCR) with marsupialization of the lacrimal sac compared with other techniques of endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy.

Material and methods: Clinical chart review. Patients with lacrimal sac pathologies and endoscopic DCR with or without marsupialization of the lacrimal sac were included from 2011 to 2015. The outcome measurements were absence of ocular symptoms and permeability of the lacrimal sac.

Results: A total of 24 patients were evaluated, 17 women and 7 men, average age was 47 years. Seven patients underwent DCR with marsupialization, 17 patients underwent other endoscopic techniques. Average follow up was 18 months. The efficacy (absence of symptoms and permeability of the lacrimal sac) of the DCR technique with marsupialization was 71%, without significant difference compared to other techniques ($p = 0.686$).

Conclusion: similar results were found in the different types of endoscopic DCR techniques. The above probably due to the small number of the sample.

Key words:

Dacryocystorhinostomy, marsupialization, lacrimal sac, endoscopy.

A Meta-analysis on Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) as Treatment for Chronic Tinnitus

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Abstract:

Tinnitus affects 10-15% of the adult population. It has no definitive treatment, and current practice guidelines favor the use of only hearing aids and sound therapy for its alleviation. Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) is a controversial new technology for its treatment, and recent studies have shown promising activity. The objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of rTMS in the treatment of patients with chronic tinnitus using the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) as outcome measure. Our study design is a meta-analysis. A systematic search of Pub med, Embase, Cochrane, and clinical trials databases were utilized to identify randomized controlled trials (RCTs) investigating the use of rTMS until August 2019. Pooled mean difference with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. Six randomized controlled trials were included in this study (N=254). Two (Folmer, Hoekstra) studies with a total of 114 participants showed a significant 2.98 reduction of THI score [CI (1.03, 4.92), Z=3.00, P=0.003] immediately after rTMS stimulation, however significant heterogeneity was noted [Chi²=9.40, P = 0.002, I²=89%]. Five studies (Billici, Formanek, Hoekstra, Marcondes, Yilmaz; Fig. 1) with a total of 190 participants showed a significant 7.38 reduction on THI scores [CI (5.75, 9.00), Z=8.91, P<0.00001] 1 month after rTMS stimulation, with no significant heterogeneity [Chi²=7.72, P = 0.10, I²=48%]. Lastly, three studies (Billici, Hoekstra, Marcondes) with a total of 99 participants showed a significant reduction of THI score by 10.22 [CI (7.25, 13.19), Z = 6.75, P < 0.00001] 6 months after rTMS stimulation, with no heterogeneity [Chi²=1.61, P = 0.45, I²=0%]. Repetitive Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (rTMS) is associated with statistically and clinically significant reduction in tinnitus severity measured by THI until 6 months post stimulation. However, more studies are needed to establish long term effects.

Key words:

Tinnitus, Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation, Meta-analysis

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the pooled mean reduction of THI at 1 month post rTMS.

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My experience in learning endoscopic ear surgeries

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Abstract:

The world has entered in era of minimal invasive surgeries with better cosmesis & less tissue handling. Endoscopic ear surgery is boon in field of otology in which most of ear diseases can be treated by transcanal approach. Main benefits are less tissue handling, no or minimal post auricular scar, wide view of endoscope, ability to visualize past the shaft of larger surgical instruments, endoscope can visualize structures that lie in the same plane & changing the magnification with the endoscope is simply achieved by moving it closer to the structure etc. Main disadvantages are 4mm endoscope perceived as too large for ear canal, One handed surgery¹ and the lack of suction with the possibility of excessive bleeding & 2 dimensional picture etc.

It takes time for ENT resident to learn skills to do endoscopic ear surgery. In my experience of 05 years after postgraduation , I practised some key factors with time which are helping me to evolve. These are examination of every patient by endoscope, use of endoscope in OPD on regular basis for removing wax, suction cleaning etc., begin with foreign body & myringotomy with grommet insertion initially, elevation of tympanomeatal flap & placing adrenaline soaked cotton ball initially than taking graft/cartilage which gives time for haemostasis, use of methylene blue² stained temporalis fascia graft which gives better differentiation with other benefits etc

It is always necessary in ever evolving medical science to share good experience & failures.

Key words:

Endoscopic ear surgeries, Methylene blue stain, Tympanoplasty, Endoscopic tympanoplasty.

Figure 1: Figure showing the methylene blue stained temporalis fascia graft placed in underlay tympanoplasty.

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The Impact of Virtual Reality Temporal Bone Simulator on Development of the Surgical Skill of identifying the surgical landmarks of mastoidectomy among The Third Year Otolaryngology Residents

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Abstract:

Purpose: Animation technology is invading the field of surgical training, especially in Otolaryngology. This study has been conducted to measure the impact of the animation technology on surgical performance of the junior trainees on the cadaveric dissection context, by identifying the ability of the residents to identify the important landmarks during a cadaveric dissection mastoidectomy.

Method: Fourteen trainees in the third year of their residency program divided randomly into two groups, group I as the experimental group and the group II as the comparison one the study was conducted only after informed detailed consent was taken from all participants and the study proposal had been approved by the ethical committee of the University of South Wales. The experimental group (5male, 2 female, and 27± 1,654 years) received four sessions of animation training on a temporal bone simulator in addition to their official ear surgery (otology) training. The comparison group (6male, 1 female, and 27± 1,654 years) received the official training only.

Results: Statistical analysis, using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), revealed that animation enhanced surgical training significantly improved the surgical skills of identification of the important landmarks of the mastoidectomy namely identification sigmoid sinus and sinodural angle, a traumatic exposure of short process of incus, identification and preservation of VII and chorda tympani and identification of epitympanic anatomy to supratubal recess. However, there was insignificant difference regarding the ability of to define cephalic edge digastric muscle with p value of 1.0000 and similarly there was statistically insignificant difference between both groups regarding identification and definition of tegmen with p value of 0.2400.

Conclusion: The applied anatomy based surgical skills improved in a statistically significant pattern among the experimental group So that it can be said that the animation technology can decrease the incidence of intra and post-operative complications caused by young trainees.

Key words:

Virtual, animation. Mastoidectomy, residents

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Innovations In Otology

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Abstract:

It remains a great challenge for all medical men to keep themselves abreast with the rapidly developing and changing scenario. In the last three decades, speciality of otolaryngology has progressed by leaps and bounds and very rapidly. It is due to the fact that there have been lot of innovations leading to minimally invasive, safe and result oriented procedures. The super speciality of otology is even much more challenging. There has been significant advances in the understanding middle ear mechanism and inner ear physiology. The innovations in Endoscopic, robotics, lasers, cochlear implants and their further developments, newer imaging modalities have been of great help to the treating physician. Many new exciting developments have emerged. Some are still in the research stage whilst others have been duly tested to be in use for the benefit of human.